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Esta peça curta trabalha com os conceitos de SMS (texto curto usado para informação, ou seja, conteúdo geralmente sem emoção). Atualmente, temos os melhores métodos de comunicação, por outro lado, nos tornamos piores nessa área, porque não a praticamos com sabedoria ou mesmo com eficácia. A peça foi escrita para ser montada internacionalmente, por isso ela foi escrita em inglês.

SMS

This short play works with the SMS concepts (short text used to deliver information, that's it, in general emotionless content). Nowadays, we have better ways of communication, however, we have become worse in this area, because we don't practice in a wisely and even efficient way.

Peça curta, monólogo, experimento e elementos épicos

Short play, monologue, experiments and epic tools.

Stage directions: This is a play about the cold sometime non-responsive text messages. It was meant to be a monologue with some audio prepared in a key moment in the end. This play should be presented as a monologue and intentionally one way audio. The text will be posted after the actor reads the message in a consecutive way. Although there will be no response, it will be showed as delivered and read. Text will be showing date and time too.

List of Characters

Taylor: She is 43 years old – very talkative and gender fluid.

Voice on the tape: A 19 year old kid who bought a second hand phone at a Parlour Pawn.

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[Jun 14, 2022, 12:58 PM]

Hey, stranger,?! When are you going to show up here?

[*You forwarded a message*]

Schedule for the Campground Activities: on July 3rd Magic show; on July 15th old cherry; on August 13th Country Singer and on August 14th petting zoo.

There will also be more things to come, like Bingo booze, Wine and dip night Ice cream sundae bar, Christmas in July and Halloween with Fireworks. I just wanted to put out there what we have booked for confirmed dates. To be totally honest with you, I'd like your kids to come, specially for petting zoo. I need some kids with me, so it won't seem creepy an almost 43 year grown up gets all excited, because of a baby goat [she gives us a loud laughter] the kids will be my excuse. [*delivered and read*]

[Jun 14, 2022, 13:28 PM]

I have a back up plan. [*pause*] I might borrow Frank's nephew and niece, but it has been a while I do not talk to them, by now, they might think I want some money. And they are not little kids any longer, but it will do it. I've still got the questions on why I never wanted to have kids. Well, I still find it selfish to have them. [*pause*] Changing subjects, as you want a spot here, if you show up, we can introduce you to the owner and it might help your case to become my neighbour. I always tell Frank that face to face interaction is way different than texting or talking over the phone. But does he listen to me? No, he does not. [*delivered and read*]

[Jun 14, 2022, 14:49 PM]

Hey, are you working today? I will shut up if you are. I have not sent you Bubly's concert tickets invitation, have I? They are being sold as ice cream in a hot summer day. I will see if there is anything left on Friday. Let me know, by then, if you are interested in buying them too, so I can find two seats near you. I am pretty sure that your boss will let you take that day off, you almost run the business without him - as you used to say it. About buying the ticket, there is a strategy behind it. As I can't afford \$125 right now. If you folks buy the tickets, and there is a single place left behind they may be selling for \$58. So Frank and I will be paying only around \$120 + taxes. Exactly what we can afford. As the regular ones would be \$255 plus taxes for both of us. Well if you want them, we can try to coordinate it on Friday. [*delivered and read*]

[Jun 14, 2022, 15:17 PM]

By the way, I get paid at 2 am on Friday. To be honest, I will be available any time in the morning, it will be great, but lots of people might be thinking like me. Okay, sorry I know you are working, keep up with those updated files and sales too. [*delivered and read*]

[Jun 14, 2022, 15:37 PM]

Ah, one more last thing that I forgot to mention, Rachel, I was about to post something to help with the amount of the tickets, I am going to sell one gift card I got for staying on the island for 3 days; to tell you the truth, I hope nothing else happens soon, because we can't afford to go back and forth anywhere else. The gas has been so crazy pricewise. We got this giftcard of a 100 dollars and I was about to post it for sales on Facebook, then I remembered that you used to go to the island with your RV, are you still going this summer? If so, I could make you a special price and you'd buy Frank's ticket. You can use it in PEI, it is valid until 2023. By the way, I don't care sitting close to Frank's seat, not that I don't love him. But my inner teenager won't give a fork if Frank will be with me or not since M.B. will be there. I have been trying to see him alive for over 10 years, and he has been to Brazil twice. I bought one ticket and I couldn't attend the concert, I got stuck in traffic jam. At the other show I was abroad, there was one time he was in New York I wish so badly I could change my fly ticket, but the concert would be the date I was leaving, I am not that crazy, lol so my celebrity crush will be here. I know he is straight and happily married to a hot woman from Argentina, but the teenager in me does not care about starring at him, it will be mandatory not awkward and for security reasons, I won't buy a meeting and greeting or somebody will be deported from Canada with a restraining order in place. Lol. Okay let me know if that would work for you, I give you the gift card, you'd buy Frank's or if you know somebody that might go they will get 100 dollar worth gift card for only 80/60 dollars depending on whom I am selling it to. [*delivered and read*]

[Jun 14, 2022, 16:16 PM]

Lastly, I need to cancel TV and phone do you happen to know some people who have our same service, I want to use that to talk our price down for just the internet. I will convince Frank to just cancel everything if it is not good in three months. We are eligible for all the services as a new customer if they didn't change the rules. Thanks and you can give me answer any day until Thursday night, because by then I will sell it to anyone and get at least my ticket. Frank does not know about Bubbly Buble he might not even want to go if

he found out about us – Bubbly(e) and I – but we had a very long history, before I met Frank he will have to understand or suck it up. Frank might found out about this later, but I do not care. I luv Bubby Singer and it is between us, yeah I know he does not have any idea that I exist, but who cares right? I have luv for both of us. Well it means his wife does not know either and so on, and I don't care he is straight. I just want him in my bedroom singing I wanna go hommmmeeee oh home. It might be on repeat not sure yet. And that is it, then after the private show he can go back to his life. Every night he would show up and it'd be our private rehearsal. By the way, I do not need an answer right away and we don't need to talk about it any longer, maybe you wanna know how 75% of white people gave birth to a guy that looks like Obama. Politically speaking I used to have a crush on Obama, meaning he is my black celebrity crush and Michelle does not need to know that, because I am nobody, but wow that woman is so powerful I have no doubt they were made for each other. I do have a crush on her too. Can you imagine to be in a bedroom with that powerful couple? OMG It gives the butterfly in my stomach only to think about it. All the conversations and lessons of life they would share with me before bed. By the way I am going to bed with them now but I need to choose with each one – Michelle or Obama? I think *Becoming Michelle* will do for my bed reading tonight.

Taylor receives a voice message and presses play: Hey, you've reached out to the wrong person, by the way, TIM! I have just bought this phone. And thanks to you, I've just got fired in my second week. Go luv yourself and take a cold shower, would you? Gee, some people's kids.

End of play

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